

instituto de astrofísica
e ciências do espaço

AMUSING ourselves with the secrets of galaxies using Integral Field Spectroscopy

IAstro Summer Internship 2023

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Galaxy Evolution: Analyzing the local and global properties to provide insights into galactic evolution over cosmic time.

Star Formation: Distribution and variation of SFRs across a galaxy can provide insights into the role of various mechanisms, such as interactions, mergers, and environmental effects, in triggering or suppressing star formation.

Motivation

Metallicity Gradient: Analysis of metallicity gradients within galaxies can provide insights into the enrichment processes, chemical evolution, and interactions with the surrounding environment.

Calibration and Benchmarking: AMUSING survey provides a valuable dataset for calibrating and benchmarking various observational techniques, analysis methods, and models used in galaxy studies.

AMUSING Survey

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graph TD; A[AMUSING Survey] --> B[All-weather]; A --> C[MUse]; A --> D[Supernova]; A --> E[Integral-field]; A --> F[Nearby]; A --> G[Galaxies];
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All-weather: Using non-optimal weather at Paranal. Average seeing of 1.1" ranging from 0.7"-1.5".

MUse: Integral Field Spectrograph mounted on VLT with spatial sampling of 0.2"×0.2" per spaxel, a FOV of 1'×1' (in WFM), and bandwidth 480–930 nm

Supernova: Aim to study SN progenitors/explosions, SN environment and all other regions within the host.

Integral-field: Obtaining a spectrum at every point (spaxel) with image-like resolution.

Nearby: Allows detailed study of gas and stellar populations.

Galaxies: Observing large sample of galaxies that have been host to SNe. Also aims to study galactic evolution and various extra-galactic studies.

Methodology

1. Binning group pixels for each galaxy, in different regions.

2. Analysing physical properties of each local group

3. Local information vs. Global data

Implications of location and size of each bin in distributions of properties:

Implications of location and size of each bin in distributions of properties:

Local vs. Global - Impact of size of Local regions

Generally, the information from larger group pixels in the central regions of galaxies tend to be closer to the global data.

Galaxy Morphological Type

Spiral galaxies

Elliptical galaxies

- AM2353-291
- ARP256
- ASASSN-13an
- ASASSN-13ch
- ASASSN-13cj
- ASASSN-13dd
- ASASSN-14at
- ASASSN-14bf
- ASASSN-14db
- ASASSN-14dz
- ASASSN-14fa
- ASASSN-14ig
- ASASSN-14jg
- 9.0 pixels
- ▲ 16 pixels
- 25.0 pixels
- + 36 pixels
- ◆ 49.0 pixels
- ⊗ 64 pixels
- ▼ 100 pixels
- ★ Global

- 2MIG_1546
- 3CO29
- ASASSN-13cp
- ASASSN-14eu_B
- 9.0 pixels
- ▲ 16 pixels
- 25.0 pixels
- + 36 pixels
- ◆ 49.0 pixels
- ⊗ 64 pixels
- ▼ 100 pixels
- ★ Global

Mass-weighted vs Light-weighted

ASASSN_14db

Mass Weighted

Light Weighted

Mean, Median or Mode ?

Galaxy ASASSN-13dd from survey dr10

Conclusions

- Precision Cosmology - Corrections to the cosmological expansion rate of the Universe could be biased;
- Our project motivates the fact that only considering global data and not grouping *spaxels*, may rise biases and errors/uncertainties to the studies of evolution of galaxies, cosmology and star formation;
- Information from larger group pixels in the central regions of galaxies tend to be closer to the global data.

Future Work

- Extending the sample to accommodate large sample of galaxies given the computational time;
- A holistic approach to all local and global properties resulting in Dark matter and dark energy corrections at the local level in the SN regions of host galaxies.
- Can be further used in cosmological corrections and understanding evolution across cosmic time.

References

- “Concerning Colour: The Effect of Environment on Type Ia Supernova Colour in the Dark Energy Survey” - <https://arxiv.org/abs/2208.01357>;
- “Dissecting Nearby Galaxies with piXedfit: I. Spatially Resolved Properties of Stars, Dust, and Gas as Revealed by Panchromatic SED Fitting” - <https://arxiv.org/abs/2110.03158>;
- “Systematic errors on optical-SED stellar mass estimates for galaxies across cosmic time and their impact on cosmology” - <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2202.04078.pdf>;

The background of the slide is a composite image. The upper right portion shows a deep space field with several galaxies, including a prominent blue spiral galaxy and a red elliptical galaxy, set against a dark sky filled with stars. The lower left portion shows a night sky with a starry background and the silhouettes of three large astronomical observatories on a dark, flat surface. One of the observatories has the number '2' on its side. A central light blue rectangular box with a black border is overlaid on the image.

Thank you!

The background of the slide is a composite image. The upper portion shows a deep space view with several galaxies, including a prominent orange-red spiral galaxy and a blue, irregularly shaped galaxy. The lower portion shows a night sky filled with stars and a nebula, with three large radio telescope dishes in the foreground. The dishes are illuminated from below, and one of them has the number '2' visible on its side.

Questions Section

Spiral Galaxies

Elliptical galaxies

